

A User-Friendly Platform for Bridging the Gap between Carbon Credit Demand and Supply

Introduction

At the beginning of CO2 Marche project, the market of additional Carbon credits was still not very popular in Italy. For that, in the context of sustainable forest management certification, was created a new platform for the voluntary sustainability credit exchange. The goal of the platform is to connect demand and supply of carbon credits deriving from Sustainable Forest Management in a voluntary trading market for tonnes of stored carbon with additionality criteria (not counted by the Italian government under the Kyoto and Paris Agreements). Also for the offer, the platform is accessible not only to the project partners, but to any operator wishing to undertake the carbon certification and counting route.

When an acquirer is interested in supporting a specific additional project, the first thing is to specifically identify the area's characteristics and the kind of activity that will be put in practice, in order to quantify the entity of the positive impacts generated. The control of the quality of the additional credits is accounted by the Inspection Body, which will annually verify compliance with the requirements of the PEFC standards.

Forests certified according to Sustainable Forest Management (SFM) are able to store more carbon than unmanaged (i.e. uncut) and untended forests; they contribute to climate change mitigation; they prevent natural and environmental hazards such as forest fires, hydrogeological disruption, soil erosion; they protect biodiversity and the landscape; they offer tourist-recreational attractions and forest products and by-products, along with culture, traditions and work for skilled forest workers.

Lessons learned

From the point of view of the ecosystem services generated, if these values were confirmed for all the certified areas of the project, Bosco di Marca Group, the active management actions would lead to the absorption of several thousand tonnes of CO₂, contributing in parallel to the creation of new business opportunities for forest managers. In fact, taking into consideration the additional actions, in terms of management (e.g. conversion of coppice to tall trees), that could be carried out in beech forests and areas with mixed deciduous trees (which account for approximately $\frac{2}{3}$ of the certified surface area), it would be possible to store up to a maximum of approximately 24,000 tonnes of CO₂ more each year (i.e. 24,000 sustainability credits). This is without taking into account the presence and increase of other co-benefits derived from Forest Sustainable Management that are not directly measured, such as increased biodiversity, improved water resource management, reduced erosion phenomena, and a positive image linked to tourism related to nature enjoyment.

For further information contact

Marco Perrino, Project Coordinator, Italy, email: marco.perrino@dream-italia.net

Francesca Giannetti, Assistant Professor, University of Florence, Italy, e-mail: francesca.giannetti@unifi.it

The information presented in this factsheet was developed by the FOREST4EU partner, drawing on the innovations and knowledge generated by the indicated operational group with their explicit authorization.

Further information

<https://www.co2marche.it/>

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